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Western-Themed Towns in China: Structural Analysis of Forgeries

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Abstract

Throughout daily life, most of us are introduced to a variety of architectural themed elements, such as replicas or forgeries that are far from their original birthplace. We often see them in hotels, shopping malls, amusement parks, in various sizes, shapes, and quantities. We experience them in passing, in the short term. However, what happens when such elements are afforded a great opportunity and freedom? Among various things, we can get themed towns. Life in China introduced me to this architectural phenomenon, through the concept of Western-themed towns, which deserves research with the purpose of discovering the fundamental ideas upon which it is based. Through various analyses, this research has covered many structural elements that make up these themed towns. Therefore, the search for a new identity of Chinese architecture, with the help of various cultural fragments, has been found to be crucial in creating the space for the birth of this phenomenon, which has many unique features.

Keywords: Architecture, China, Fake, Forgery, Replica, Mimicry, Copycat, Kitsch

1. Aims

The first aim of this research paper is to show the culture of 'copying' in China, why replicas of famous architectural works from Western countries have appeared there, and to discover the fundamental ideas and reasons behind it. The second aim of this research paper is to show and share, through visual and textual analyzes of carefully selected case studies, how successfully these cities have been designed, from the architectural point of view.

2. Introduction

2.1 Importance of the research

China's incredible economic development over the last few decades has led to mass urbanization, which is characterized by constant growth. The rural population inhabits large urban centers. However, this transformation causes a very expensive life. This naturally leads to the development of suburban areas. In order to activate suburban regions of large urban centers and to attract people there, Western-themed towns appeared. In other words, themed towns are replicas of other cities, their copies.

We can recognize architectural replications all over the world. Copying buildings or imitating a particular style of architecture is nothing new. But copying entire cities, that's unique, that's new, and therefore it is important to be researched.

2.2 Need and purpose of the research

It is necessary to point out that these projects are not only replicas of Western cities, but they are usually inauthentic replicas. These towns have no history. All of their visual value fits into their facades, which are there to provide an international atmosphere and an image of wealth.

These Western-themed projects are also receiving a lot of media attention. Various media sources from around the world have given them so much free advertising and exposure, and consequently, they have become known to the general public. Thus, this developed their tourism potential, and at the same time opened the door for many discussions.

Besides all of the mentioned features, these towns are Chinese towns, even if they are inspired by Western styles. These are places where families live, where children grow up, where they spend their free time, where they learn, etc. Therefore, the most crucial part for the life of citizens is the structure of each town, not its appearance. From there, with the purpose to find, to differentiate, to bring together, to overview, various analyses of these structures are the need of this research.

2.3. A brief preview of the research

This research is divided into two major parts. The first major part is a review of the literature, which is based on published works related to the chosen topic. The focus of this section is on seeking answers to carefully selected questions, in order to fully present and understand the topic.

The second major part is case studies, which deal with various analyzes of carefully selected examples, in order to extract the main characteristics of their structures. These case studies have focused on general site analysis, natural conditions and potentials, historical analysis, land use analysis, building structure analysis and transportation analysis.

3. Literature Review

The first aim of this literature review was to build my knowledge and advance my understanding of this topic. The second and main aim of this literature review is to demonstrate this knowledge and update all readers about this subject. This literature review is based on information from published books and research papers, and the literature is selected on its relevance to answer the following questions:

1. Why kitsch is the foundation of forgeries nowadays?
2. How do we define 'forgery'?
3. What was the purpose of copies and forgeries throughout history?
4. What are the characteristics of the culture of 'copying' in China?
5. What can we learn from the 'Western Themed Cities' projects in China?

3.1. Why kitsch is the foundation of forgeries nowadays?

When we mention the word 'forgery', it is very easy to find synonyms such as fake, replica, mimicry, copycat... Nowadays, these terms are seen as side effects of the kitsch. Therefore, first, we must clarify the idea of kitsch, and why forgery is identified as its result.

According to Kulka (2002), we use the term kitsch very often, and we presume that its meaning is reasonably clear, but when we want to define kitsch, we can see that it is not an easy task and that many authors who have tried to analyze its concept have soon noted its extraordinary complexity and elusiveness. Although it is difficult to make a short and clear definition of kitsch, a strong link between copying and counterfeiting with kitsch is created during the beginning of the mass production of art goods. According to Emmer (1998) mass production evolved with members of the 'lower' classes, whos only purchase kitsch because it is an imitation of 'upper' class art forms, and they would like to have the appearance of belonging to that class. This is supported by the research of Binkley (2000) who detected three ways in which kitsch aestheticizes repetition, and the first one is an emulation of cultural products, which often copies the signs of class status.

Consequently, the art goods that were considered tasteful started to be copied. But that created a new side effect. Ward (1991) pointed out that copying of what was regarded as tasteful creates objects of no value because they became common. In the book written by Dorfles & Machale (1969), this was explained as degradation of whole original values to the level of kitsch symbol, after which the piece that was intended to remain unique, is recognized not by its real qualities, but for a sentimental or technical substitute of these values.

Therefore, we can conclude that today's forgeries are the product of the kitsch culture, that supports the mass reproduction of artworks, that cause decreasing of their real values and creating new values that make them being recognized as kitsch symbols.

3.2. How do we define 'forgery'?

Even when we easily recognize and understand terms such as forgery, fake or copy, it is not easy to set their short and clear definitions, because of their complexity and intertwining between themselves.

In an article written by Gaiger (2001), we can find the following definition: 'Forgery undermines the modern concept of art, ridiculing and deglorifying the notions of illimitability, uniqueness, and originality on which it is based.' (p. 339). According to Negrich (2011), there is a clear difference between a fake and a forgery, and he expressed it as the difference between mere copying and intentional deceit. Negrich easily explained it through an example: 'If artist B copies the work of artist A at the same time that artist A creates his work then the work of artist B could not be a forgery. However, if artist B copied the work two decades after the original work was created then the work could be a forgery. Even though artist B could have the exact same intentions for his work in each example, the above definition of forgeries treats the two cases differently' (p. 3).

3.3. What was the purpose of copies and forgeries throughout history?

'Until the nineteenth century, the copy of an original work had its own value, it was a legitimate practice. In our own time, the copy is illegitimate, inauthentic: it is no longer "art." Similarly, the concept of forgery has changed - or rather, it suddenly appears with the advent of modernity.' (Scott, 2016, p. 84).

According to Negrich (2011), forgers seem to have existed during the second millennium before the current era, and they were the Phoenicians who trafficked in art forgeries and lived near the Mediterranean and the Adriatic sea. Negrich also mentioned that many artists for centuries openly copied works and styles of known artists, and this was often seen as a manifestation of respect and honor for the original artist.

Gaiger (2001) points out, in his article, that throughout the Classical period, the works of celebrated Greek artists served as prototypes for other artists, and the culture of 'copying' of Greek works was continuous with a long-standing tradition.

3.4. What are the characteristics of the culture of 'copying' in China?

Fong (1962) highlighted that forgery in China has never carried such dark connotations as it does in the West, and the legal or ethical problems never appeared since the aim of studying art has always been either aesthetic cultivation or pure enjoyment, so the ability to create a perfect forgery of masterpieces was a matter of virtuosity and pride. Fong also pointed out that copying in ancient China was not only an honorable but also a vitally necessary form of art because it was the only way to reproduce, circulate and perpetuate treasured masterpieces.

Lin (2011) pointed out that copying is an integral part of Chinese culture because traditional Chinese Confucian education required reciting and copying, therefore, it was essential for students to learn to copy.

3.5. What can we learn from the 'Western Themed Cities' projects in China?

'Situated in a vast ring around the city, the nine towns will eventually house a population of more than 500 000 people. Hand-picked foreign architects have designed the towns, each meant to evoke the urbanism of a different Western nation, including Italy, Spain, England, the United States, Sweden, the Netherlands, Australia, New Zealand, and Germany. Known as 'One City, Nine Towns', the project began as a pipe dream of former Shanghai Communist Party Secretary Huang Ju, who conceived of the themed towns as a way to celebrate Shanghai's history as a global city' (Campanella, 2012, p.88). Large-scale projects like 'One City, Nine Towns' allow us to better understand the culture of copying in China's modern architecture, and the reasons behind it.

It is true that large projects based on replicas were also occurring in other areas but in a different context. Often, in certain cities, based on their traditional architecture, a trend of fake historic buildings appears as a way of promoting tourism or encouraging revitalization. This was researched by Levi (2005), who concluded that this kind of fake architecture is contextual, and it supports community aesthetics by increasing the historic character of a city.

According to Campanella (2012), these kind of projects in China are about selling a lifestyle, not just a home, and it is caused by extreme competition in the property market, where developers copying ideas and motives from elsewhere, in search of anything that will make their real estates attractive.

According to Hartog (2010) thematically parts can be seen as a reaction to the lack of identity from which many new cities suffer, but they also have a germinal function, stimulating larger-scale development. Hartog points out that the international influence in architecture and urbanism is hoped to attract the prosperous Chinese middle class, and even create a tourist value because due to poor air quality, more and more Chinese escape from the city during the weekend to visit historical towns and parks.

Lin (2011) points out that this copying practice in China nowadays is a result of the government's willingness to foster multiculturalism. But at the same time, and contradictory, we have an internet blockade in China, that is according to Roberts (2018), made from a desire to censor and suppress negative information, and it completely blocks multiculturalism.

Why do citizens support projects like this by buying the properties? There are two phenomena that may be the reason for that. The first phenomenon is explained by Knapp (2000), who mentioned that construction boom in China over past two decades has led to the destruction of countless humble as well as fine old dwellings, and this was also supported by their residents and others who regard them as too ordinary, outdated, and dysfunctional to maintain. The second phenomenon is a Western influence on Chinese values and it is explained by Capen (1913), who wrote that with the influence of western governments western lifestyle, values, knowledge, thoughts, and achievements have been spread in China, especially among students and the progressive classes. If we combine these two phenomena, we will have perfect buyers for real estates of Western replicas, who will enjoy Western brands and lifestyles.

According to Bosker (2013) China has billions of square feet dedicated to projects of themed towns, and these homes in subtle but important ways shaping the behavior of their occupants because they are designed as permanent habitat to hundreds of thousands of Chinese, who will raise children, wash cars, cook dinners, and live out their daily routines here, but in accordance with Western lifestyle, values, and rituals. Bosker points out that this replication program goes beyond architecture and construction techniques, and it recreates not only the superficial appearance of Western historical cities, but also the atmospheric and experiential local color of the originals through such devices as foreign names, signage, and lifestyle amenities. Bosker also points out that the foundations of these projects are Chinese technology, mechanical and infrastructural capability, financial resources, powerful government support and clients from a growing middle class, which includes a population of between 100 million and 250 million consumers. Bosker concluded that all off this give force to ingenuity and innovation, and it's just a part of the process of seeking a new identity in Chinese architecture.

According to Zhao (2018), in 2016, the Chinese government released a document that requires for all new buildings to be suitable, economic, green and pleasing to the eye, but despite all this, William Shakespeare's historic hometown was recreated as part of a new tourist town called San Weng, in Jiangxi province. Zhao also mentioned that at first, these cities had a small population, so they were named 'Ghost Towns', but now they are very populated, they function normally and even developing with the construction of subways, etc.

3.6. The conclusion from the literature review

After summarizing the entire literature from this review, we can conclude that forgeries in China are often seen as the manifestation of respect and honor for the original work and as technological, mechanical and infrastructural capability of the country. We can also conclude that ideas behind creating Western-themed towns are seen as the

spread of multiculturalism, as the creation of a global character in cities, as the provider of new lifestyles, and this phenomenon is seen as part of the process of seeking and creating a new identity in Chinese architecture.

4. Case Studies: Aim & Methods

The main aim of these case studies is to do analyzes and then, in relation to the results of these analyses, to make comparisons, conclusions, and arguments related to the selected topic. We are in a time when we are striving for sustainable, creative, smart cities, with a focus on social efficiency, education, innovation, communication, technology, etc. Therefore, for the case studies, I chose Sky City and Thames Town, as these are themed towns created in the recent past, and adequately present and describe the phenomenon of Western-themed cities in China. Through various analyses, I want to show the development of these themed towns and draw conclusions about their structure, characteristics, and impacts from an architectural point of view.

I used several working methods for this research. I mostly relied on visual analysis, which I supplemented with textual analysis and historical analysis. Therefore, I was able to write my observations and draw some conclusions and finally enrich them with the help of textual data.

5. Case Study: Sky City

5.1. General Site Analysis

Sky City is located in the suburban area of Hangzhou, about 18 kilometers from the center of the capital of Zhejiang Province, China. The city began to develop around 2007, with the construction of a Western French-themed town. Since then, this is the center of development of the area, with a current population of about 40 000 people, dominated by Han people. The political authority, plan, and project of Hangzhou conditioned the economic development of this suburban area today. In 2019, Sky City received the provincial 'Urban Leader Award', for its strong strength in real estate development, outstanding contribution to the Hangzhou property market, and social development.

Table 1: General information about Sky City

General Info	Value
Chinese name:	Tiāndūchéng (天都城)
Foreign name:	Tiandu city / Sky City
Country:	China
Province:	Zhejiang (浙江)
City:	Hangzhou (杭州)
District:	Yuhang (余杭)
Address:	Xingqiao Street (星桥街道)
Development:	Since 2007.
Development cycle:	20 years
Town's area:	7600 acres (about 31km ²)
Construction area:	4.8 million m ²
Total investment:	10 billion 元 (about 1.28 billion €)
Planned population:	80 000 to 100 000 citizens
Current population:	40 000 citizens
Distance from the city center:	18 km

5.2. Natural conditions and potentials

The location is characterized by low terrain, dense river networks and dense lakes, rich in products, and has the typical characteristics of a 'south of Yangtze river' area.

Sky City is located in the subtropical monsoon region and belongs to the subtropical monsoon climate, with four distinct seasons and abundant rainfall. The annual average temperature is 17.8 ° C, the average relative humidity is 70.3%, the annual rainfall is 1454 mm, and the annual sunshine hours are about 1765 hours. Summers are hot and humid. In contrast, winters are cold and dry. The spring and autumn climate is pleasant, and it is the golden season for sightseeing.

The area of Hangzhou is rich in products and it is known as the 'Home of fish and rice'. The agricultural production conditions are unique, with a wide variety of crops, forest trees, livestock and poultry, and more than 260 varieties of forest fruits, tea mulberries, and flowers.

5.3. Historical Analysis

Sky City is a new city, little more than a decade old, purposefully planned and designed for suburban development, and therefore it is very limited in the terms of historical analysis.

There are no records and events in recent history that had implications for the spatial development of the selected area. The urban and architectural evolution of location followed a pre-planned development that was conditioned by settling a newly created city (Figure 1 & Figure 2). There is not cultural and historical heritage or protected area of the site that can impact future designs or development. The existing context of buildings in the city is a mix of thematic Western styles and the contemporary style of Chinese social housing architecture, with a lack of traditional building experience.

Figure 1: Aerial views of the location from 2003.

Figure 2: Aerial views of the location from 2019.

5.4. Analysis of land use structure

The purpose of this analysis is to discover the real land uses that exist or predominate within the selected area of investigation and the interrelation of different land uses. Available material and data from the Baidu Maps platform were used for the analysis.

The results of the analysis are presented graphically in the following attachment (Figure 5), and according to them the dominant spatial unit, ie. the dominant use of the land is residential, while the educational use of land is to a lesser extent. Other land uses, like a commercial, health care, etc. exist in the near or far area, but not within the boundaries of analysis. In developed areas, we can recognize public open spaces, semi-public open spaces and private open spaces.

Within the selected location there are areas that are not yet developed or are under development. The current developing area is also planned as a residential zone.

5.5. Analysis of building structures

The purpose of this analysis is to discover building structures and provide information on the function that exists or predominate within the selected area of investigation. In the selected location we can distinguish four zones in which there are different groups of objects, with a dominant residential purpose. Zones are shown graphically in the following attachment (Figure 5). The available material and data from the Baidu Maps platform were used for the analysis.

Figure 3: Sky City (left half) and Paris (right half)

Figure 4: Sky City (left half) and Paris (right half)

Zone 1 is characterized by buildings that are thematically inspired by the Western French architecture and motifs of Paris (Figure 3 & Figure 4). The number of stories is low, usually less than 8 floors. The main purpose of the buildings is residential and can be described as a large multi-family (apartments/flats) zone. Ground floor uses may be for commercial purposes. Buildings are characterized by spaces with a closed or open character and spaces formed by geometrical edges. In this zone, we can identify good relationships of form and mass, scale and proportion, rhythm and repetition, and geometry and hierarchy. On buildings, we can recognize stylistic elements and a lot of facade ornaments and decorations. This is the first built zone and it served as a prerequisite for the development of this area. Zone one is also characterized by French style streets. The whole building complex with art shops, various forms of street performances, sculptures, paintings, etc., provide a charming scenery of a French rural town.

Zone 2 is characterized by buildings that are thematically inspired by Western American architecture. The number of stories is low, usually less than 7 floors. The main purpose of the buildings is residential and can be described as single-family / multi-family attached (mansions) zone. Buildings are characterized by private spaces with closed character. In this zone, we can identify good relationships of private space, structure, and proportion.

Zone 3 and Zone 4 are characterized by buildings that are built according to modern Chinese social housing architecture. The number of stories in zone 3 is usually less than 7 floors. The number of stories in zone 4 is usually higher than 12 floors. The main purpose of the buildings in zone 3 and zone 4 is residential and can be described as a large multi-family (apartments/flats) zone. In zone 4 we have buildings that are under development. All buildings in all zones were built after 2007, and therefore this is a newly built area.

5.6. Analysis of the transport structures

Roads as public spaces and traffic structures are crucial for space perception. Therefore the purpose of this analysis is to discover existing transport facilities within the selected area of investigation and its connection and integration into the transport networks. Available material and data from the Baidu Maps platform were used for the analysis. According to the analysis at the selected location, there are streets with different proportions, clear divisions of driving lanes and side areas, different types, shapes and sizes of road spaces, appropriate traffic furniture, materials, and lighting equipment (Figure 5). Therefore, traffic in the selected location is characterized by satisfactory capacity and user-friendliness. The type of transport is passenger, while purpose and distances can be described as internal transport.

Traffic is characterized by very good circulation, within and around the site, good access, and good accessibility for persons with disabilities. We can identify multiple types of used transportation at the selected location, and therefore we can recognize motorized traffic, local public transport, cycle traffic, foot traffic and dormant traffic (parking spaces). All of them create a hierarchical network, so the traffic is evenly distributed. Construction of Metro Line 3, which connects Sky City to Hangzhou, started in early 2018, and it is still under development.

Figure 5: Graphical presentation of the structural analysis of Sky City

6. Case Study: Thames Town

6.1. General Site Analysis

Thames Town is located in the Songjiang District, in the core area of Songjiang New Town, about 30 kilometers from the center of Shanghai in China. The city began to develop in 2001 and it had three phases. During 2001-

2003 the city was designed by the architectural firm 'Atkins Design Studio', with a British theme for 10 000 inhabitants. During 2003-2004 the infrastructure and main facilities were built and in the period 2004-2006, all residential buildings were built. In 2004, Thames Town won the title of Shanghai's 2004 Most Investment Potential Real Estate.

The overall layout of Thames Town, from brick to tile, reflects the original European British town style. The city is named after the river Thames from London. The town consists mostly of single-family housing, such as single villas and multi-story apartments, with few commercial or community facilities. It also consists of continuous multifunctional pedestrian streets and a lakeside British style square. Some of the architecture was directly copied from buildings found in England, including the main square church, pubs, and shops.

All the houses sold very quickly. However, the clientele was relatively wealthy, so the homes were bought as investments or other homes, so the number of citizens was low. That is why in the beginning the Thames Town was nicknamed as 'Ghost town'.

Thames town took full advantage of the good ecological environment of the Shenjing pond, and now with a green coverage rate of 60%, it is a large community with multiple functions such as living, tourism, and leisure. Like every other Western Themed Town in China, it has become very popular as a wedding photography location, because it provides foreign backgrounds.

If we look at the microsite of Thames Town, it is located between the residential area and the business area of Songjiang New Town. In the immediate location of Thames Town, there are 'Shanghai Harmony Kindergarten', 'Songjiang Primary School', 'Sanxin Primary School', 'Songjiang University Town', shopping malls, hospitals, post offices, banks, 'Sixian Park', 'Central Park'. Near the selected location there are no hazards and facilities that produce a certain level of pollution, noise, smoke, odors, etc.

Table 2: General information about Thames Town

General Info	Value
Chinese name:	Tàiwùshìxiǎozhèn (泰晤士小镇)
Foreign name:	Thames Town
Country:	China
Municipality:	Shanghai (上海)
District:	Songjiang (松江)
Development:	2001-2006
Client / Developer	Shanghai Hengmao Real Estate Co.
Designer	Atkins Design Studio
Town's area:	1km ²
Construction area:	500 000 m ²
Green coverage rate:	60%
Total investment:	5 billion 元 (about 640 million €)
Planned population (by 2020):	10 000 citizens
Distance from the city center:	41 km

6.2. Natural conditions and potentials

The location is characterized by low terrain and its territory belongs to the Yangtze River Delta Plain. There are also low mountain hills zones in some surrounding areas.

The proximity of the small lake Shenjing provides natural views, and sensory qualities and variations of light, sound, and smell. The surrounding area is characterized by the dense river and lake networks.

Thames Town belongs to the northern subtropical monsoon region and its climate is affected by alternating warm and cold air. The climate is warm and humid, with four distinct seasons, abundant rain, sufficient sunshine, and long frost-free period. The annual average temperature is 15.4 °C. The annual average precipitation is 1103.2 mm and there are on average 137 rainy days. The rainy season is from June to July, with an average of about 20 days. Autumns and winters are foggy.

The natural environment of the area of Songjiang is characterized by medicinal plants, different types of bamboo, fruit trees, and herbal flowers.

6.3. Historical Analysis

Songjiang District has a longer and richer history than the old city of Shanghai and has been a major trading hub in the Yangtze Delta region for centuries. However, Songjiang New City is part of a new wave of development aimed at diverting the population from central Shanghai and activating suburban areas (Figure 6 & Figure 7). Within that wave of development, the 'One City, Nine Towns' project was born, which aimed to create nine new West-themed towns, in the suburban area of Shanghai. Thus, Thames Town was born in Songjiang New City as a result of an international competition won by British architectural firm Atkins. Therefore, Thames Town is generally a fresh project, so it is very limited in historical analysis.

Thames Town was envisioned as an attractive suburban residential environment for professors affiliated with the than freshly-built Songjiang University Town that had the capacity of a total of 150 000 students. In addition to providing accommodation, Thames Town is also conceived as a tourist resource. Therefore, Thames Town can be seen as a fully marketable project, with the idea of reaching Western quality and lifestyle standards.

Thames Town has come a long way since being seen as a failure in the industry. The reason for this was that it was too far from Shanghai during the construction period. However, with the developed economy and transportation, things have changed dramatically. As the population in Songjiang New City increased, the occupancy of Thames Town increased too. This has also transformed Thames Town into an urban tourism destination.

There are no records and events in recent history that would affect the spatial development of the selected area. The urban and architectural evolution of the site followed a pre-planned project and plan, with a clearly defined goal. There is no cultural and historical heritage or protected area of the site that may affect future design or development. The existing context of city buildings is in line with the British theme.

Figure 6: Aerial views of the location from 2008.

Figure 7: Aerial views of the location from 2019.

6.4. Analysis of land use structure

The purpose of this analysis is to discover the real land uses that exist or predominate within the selected area of investigation and the interrelation of different land uses. Available material and data from the Baidu Maps platform were used for the analysis.

The results of the analysis are presented graphically in the following attachment (Figure 10), and according to them the dominant spatial unit, ie. the dominant use of the land is residential, with different building types such as individual houses, terraced houses, and multi-story buildings. At the site, we can also find other land uses, like educational zone, commercial zone, health care zone, public green space, tourist zone, etc. Also, all other land uses can be found in the immediate vicinity of the analyzed location.

At the selected location we can recognize open public spaces (public square, public green space, lakeside area...), public open spaces associated with certain facilities (educational zone), semi-public open spaces (the inner courtyards of apartment complexes), private open spaces (gardens). Open public spaces provide natural spatial experience and qualities. They have recreational and functional value. The interaction of open space and housing structure is defined by proportional surface area and spatial distribution.

6.5. Analysis of building structures

The purpose of this analysis is to discover building structures and provide information on the function that exists or predominate within the selected area of investigation. The available material and data from the Baidu Maps platform were used for the analysis. Zones are shown graphically in the following attachment (Figure 10).

The city of Thames is modeled after a traditional rural British village. All buildings have different heights and there is no repetition in terms of design. According to local building regulations, all buildings have a concrete frame and are finished with decorative brick and tile leather. All other materials and furniture were imported from Britain. In the selected location we can distinguish four zones in which there are different groups of objects, with a dominant residential purpose.

The entire town has a total construction area of 500 000 square meters. From the perspective of volume distribution, Thames Town has closed residential areas, open residential buildings, open commercial and residential areas, commercial blocks, office buildings, schools, hotels, health centers, fitness clubs, etc. It is planned that all buildings meet the criteria in terms of form, structure, scale and proportion, rhythm and repetition, hierarchy, public space and private space.

Zone 1 is characterized by single-family detached individual housing. The main purpose of the buildings is residential. The predominant types of buildings are villas.

Zone 2 is characterized by buildings of a few floors. The main purpose of the buildings is residential (Figure 8 & Figure 9). The predominant types of buildings are low-rise apartments.

Zone 3 is characterized by buildings with mixed commercial and residential purpose and different ground floor uses. This zone contains buildings of three to six floors. The first (ground) floor is usually a business area, and other floors are housing. The main business formats are lively and long-term business types, such as catering, bars, the wedding industry, and galleries.

Zone 4 consists of buildings that are not intended for residential use, but those buildings that are classified as an educational, commercial, commercial, tourist, etc. These buildings vary in shape, height, mass... It is important to point out a replica of Bristol Cathedral which is located at the open public square.

Figure 8: View from Zone 2 towards Public Square

Figure 9: Different British-themed facades in Zone 2

6.6. Analysis of the transport structures

The purpose of this analysis is to discover existing transport facilities and characteristics within the selected area of investigation and its connection and integration into the transport networks. Available material and data from the Baidu Maps platform were used for the analysis.

According to the analysis at the selected location, there are streets with different proportions, types, shapes and sizes of road spaces, satisfactory capacity, appropriate traffic furniture, materials, and lighting equipment (Figure 10). The transport system meets all needs in terms of circulation, access to location and accessibility within a location. Different street patterns and different types of streets are recognized, ranging in width from 4.5 meters to 25 meters. This is shown graphically in the following attachment (Figure 6).

Thames Town is an organically grown town, and its concept was to create a sense of community through its hierarchy of open spaces with streets and squares. Therefore the main transportation feature of Thames Town, and what immediately catches your attention, is the transportation system produced by a continuous multifunctional pedestrian street and a lakeside British-style square. This type of transportation network allows and creates a good place for residents and tourists to meet, perform, relax, and socialize.

The streets, which are often no more than 6 meters to 10 meters wide, are pedestrianized. These are moderate to low-use roads. With an aim to free the town's center, several underground car parking areas have been constructed, and they represent dormant traffic. These areas also serve as emergency shelters. There are no transport areas that are particularly inconvenient or dangerous.

It is important to point out that the establishment of several rail transit stations, such as Songjiang New Town rail station and University Town rail station, has greatly changed the situation of Thame Town and increased its occupancy rate.

Figure 10: Graphical presentation of the structural analysis of Thames Town

7. Conclusion

After summarizing the entire literature from this review and after summarizing the results of analyses of selected case studies, we can conclude that all main goals of this research work have been successfully fulfilled.

We can conclude that forgeries in China can be seen as the manifestation of respect and honor for original works and, as a part of the process of seeking and creating a new identity in Chinese architecture, they serve to create a multicultural character in the city.

According to the research of case studies, we can conclude that Western-themed cities are being built in different parts of China characterized by different natural conditions. They are mainly built in suburban areas, with the aim of attracting citizens with their international appearance, thus enabling further development of the area. The

dominant land use in these towns is residential, while all other required land uses (educational, commercial, health care...) are located within or around the site.

Due to the small population immediately after construction, each town was nicknamed as 'Ghost Town'. However, with the construction of metros and the improvement of transport infrastructure, the accessibility of the towns became better, thus the population sharply increased and enabled further, previously planned, development.

Considering that all these towns are made with the aim of creating and presenting Western identities, characteristics, and atmosphere through architecture, we can come across many different building structures, which primarily differ in chosen Western appearance, and then in dimensions, materials, etc.

And finally, as these cities provide international backgrounds, they have caused the rapid growth of the wedding industry in these locations, much more than other businesses. Also, these cities have great tourism potential.

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Figures:

Figure 1: Google Earth. [Image].

Figure 2: Google Earth. [Image].

Figure 3: [Image]. Retrieved from <http://shorturl.at/nuJQ2>

Figure 4: [Image]. Retrieved from <http://shorturl.at/joqN3>

Figure 6: Google Earth. [Image].

Figure 7: Google Earth. [Image].

Figure 8: [Image]. Retrieved from <https://youimg1.c-ctrip.com/target/1A031a00000194bz5A245.jpg>

Figure 9: [Image]. Retrieved from <https://youimg1.c-ctrip.com/target/100g12000000rth2z7CC4.jpg>

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